

**“IQTISODIY TADQIQOTLARGA
ASOSLANGAN OLIY MA’LUMOTLI
IQTISODCHI KADRLARNI
TAYYORLASH: MUAMMOLAR VA
INNOVATSION YECHIMLAR”
MAVZUSIDAGI**

**XALQARO ILMIY-AMALIY
KONFERENSIYA
MATERIALLARI TO‘PLAMI**

I

**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY TA’LIM, FAN VA
INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI
BUXORO VILOYATI HOKIMLIGI
BUXORO DAVLAT UNIVERSITETI**

**“Iqtisodiy tadqiqotlarga asoslangan oliy ma’lumotli iqtisodchi
kadrlarni tayyorlash: muammolar va innovatsion yechimlar”
mavzusidagi**

**xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya materiallari to`plami, 2023 yil 6-7
iyun
I JILD**

**Collection of materials of the international scientific and practical
conference "Training highly educated economists based on
economic research: problems and innovative solutions", June 6-7,
2023
I VOLUME**

**Сборник материалов международной научно-практической
конференции «Подготовка высокообразованных экономистов
на основе экономических исследований: проблемы и
инновационные решения», 6-7 июня 2023 г.
ТОМ I**

Buxoro – Bukhara – Бухара – 2023

УДК: 631.1:339.13(575.1)

“Iqtisodiy tadqiqotlarga asoslangan oliy ma’lumotli iqtisodchi kadrlarni tayorlash: muammolar va innovatsion yechimlar”. Xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi to’plami. 2023 yil 6-7 iyun: - Buxoro : “Sadridin Salim Buxoriy” Durdona Nashriyoti, 2023.-765 b.

1. Qo`yidagi tarkibdan iborat dasturiy qo`mita

1. O.X. Xamidov – Buxoro davlat universiteti rektori, rais;
2. T.Rasulov – Ilmiy ishlar va innovatsiyalar bo`yicha prorektor, rais muovini;
3. D. Sh. Yavmutov – Iqtisodiyot va turizm fakulteti dekani, i.f.n, dotsent, a`zo;
4. J.R. Toxirov – Marketing va menejment kafedrası mudiri v.b., i.f.f.d., a`zo;
5. B.N. Navruz-Zoda – Marketing va menejment kafedrası professori, i.f.d., psofessor, a`zo;
6. N.S.Ibragimov – Turizm va si mudiri, xo`jaligi kafedrası mudiri, i.f.d., professor, a`zo;
7. A.J. Abdullayev – Iqtisodiyot kafedrası mudiri, i.f.f.d., professor, a`zo;
8. G.R. Xidirova – Marketing va menejment kafedrası doktoranti, i.f.f.d, a`zo;
9. D.X.Xodjayeva – Marketing va menejment kafedrası katta o`qituvchisi, a`zo;
10. A.T.Jo`rayev – Xalqaro aloqalar bo`yicha prorektor, i.f.n, a`zo;
11. S.C. Davlatov – Iqtisodiyot kafedrası katta o`qituvchisi, a`zo;
12. Z.T. Jo`rayeva – Marketing va menejment kafedrası katta o`qituvchisi, kotib.

1. Qo`yidagi tarkibdan iborat tashkiliy qo`mita

1. T. Rasulov – Ilmiy ishlar va innovatsiyalar bo`yicha prorektor, rais;
 2. D. Sh. Yavmutov – Iqtisodiyot va turizm fakulteti dekani, i.f.n, dotsent, rais muovini;
 3. O`. Umarov – Moliya va iqtisodiyot ishlari bo`yicha prorektor, a`zo;
 4. G.T. Zaripov – I va IPKTB bo`limi boshlig`i, a`zo;
 5. N.S.Ibragimov – Turizm va si mudiri, xo`jaligi kafedrası mudiri, i.f.d., professor, a`zo;
 6. J.R. Toxirov – Marketing va menejment kafedrası mudiri v.b., i.f.f.d., a`zo;
 7. A.J. Abdullayev – Iqtisodiyot kafedrası mudiri, i.f.f.d., professor, a`zo;
 8. H.Ziyovutdinov – Marketing va menejment kafedrası tayanch doktoranti, a`zo;
 9. L.B.Navruz-zoda – Marketing va menejment kafedrası dotsent v.b., i.f.f.d., a`zo.
 10. S.U.Tadjiyeva – Marketing va menejment kafedrası dotsenti, i.f.n., a`zo.
 11. Z.T. Jo`rayeva – Marketing va menejment kafedrası katta o`qituv, kotib.
- To`plam i.f.d. professor, B.N. Navro`z-Zoda umumiy tahriri ostida chop etildi.

Mazkur to`plamga kiritilgan ilmiy ishlar va g`oyalar mazmuni, undagi statistik ma`lumotlar, sanalarning aniqligiga hamda tanqidiy fikr-mulohazalarga mualliflarning shaxsan o`zlari mas`uldirlar.

Мазкур Халқаро илмий-амалий конференция Ўзбекистон Республикаси олий таълим, фан ва инновациялар вазирининг 2023 йил 2 майдаги 118-сон буйруғига асосан Бухоро давлат университетида Янги Зеландиянинг Веллингтон Викториа университети, Россия Федерациясининг Санкт-Петербург иқтисодий университети ва Қозон Федерал университети, Тожикистон Миллий университети, Қозоғистоннинг Л.Н. Гумилев номидаги Евроосиё миллий университети, Қирғизистоннинг С.Нааматов номидаги Нарин давлат университети, Украинанинг иқтисодий ва технологиялар университети ва Алфраганус университети билан ҳамкорликда *иқтисодий фанлари доктори, профессор Б.Н. Навруз- Зоданинг илмий фаолиятининг 50 йиллиги ва таваллудининг 70 йиллик юбилейига* бағишланган.

Согласно приказу Министра высшего образования, науки и инноваций Республики Узбекистан за №118 от 2 мая 2023 г., Бухарский государственный университет совместно с университетом Виктории Веллингтон (Новая Зеландия), Санкт-Петербургским экономическим и Казанским Федеральным университетами (РФ), Национальным университетом Таджикистана, Евроазиатским национальным университетом имени Л.Н.Гумилёва (Казахстан), Наринским государственным университетом имени С.Нааматова, Украинским университетом экономики и технологии и университетом Алфрагануса организован *Международная научно-практическая конференция посвящённая 50-летию научной деятельности и 70-летию со дня рождения доктора экономических наук, профессора Бахтияра Негматовича Навруз- Зода.*

The international scientific-practical conference organized by official decree of the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 118 dated May 2, 2023, Bukhara State University and Victoria Wellington University (New Zealand), St. Petersburg Economic and Kazan Federal University (RF), National University of Tajikistan, Eurasian National University named after L.N. Gumilyova (Kazakhstan), Naryn State University named after S. Naamatova, Ukrainian University of Economics and Technology and University of Alfraganusa dedicated to the 50th anniversary of Navruz-Zoda's scientific activity and the 70th anniversary of his birth.

- ✓ Ma'lumotlar to'g'ri, strukturaviy, aniq, oddiy, maqsadli guruhga moslangan va ustuvorliklarga yo'naltirilgan bo'lishi lozim;
- ✓ Topshiriqlarni tashkil etishda Blum taksonomiyasini inobatga olgan holda topshiriq bosqichlaridan foydalanish.
- ✓ Dars jarayonida teskari aloqa (feedback) dan foydalanish.

Zamonaviy yetuk malakali kadrlar har qaysi davlatning iqtisodiy rivojlanishiga ma'lum ma'noda o'z hissasini qo'shishi shubhasizdir. Shuning uchun ham ta'lim tizimiga muntazam ravishda yangi ilg'or zamonaviy texnologiyalarni joriy etish shart va zarur deb hisoblaymiz.

ADABIYOTLAR RO'YXATI.

1. Entrepreneurship and Business Development (Textbook for EBD-Students): Erasmus+ CACTLE (Central Asian Center for Teaching, Learning and Entrepreneurship) 244 final, Vienna: European Union, 2018.
2. Лисина М.И. Общение, личность и психика ребенка // Под ред. А.Рузской. –М.: 2007.
3. [tps://management.cactle.eu/course/WP3.1-Certified University Teacher.: workbook-2016](https://management.cactle.eu/course/WP3.1-Certified%20University%20Teacher.:%20workbook-2016)
4. Teaching and Learning at Universities (Promoting good teaching to promote good learning in a changing society) Erasmus+ Collective Monography 243 final, Vienna: European Union, 2018.
5. Golish L.V., D.M. Fayzullayeva "Pedagogik texnologiyalarni loyihalash va rejalash" Toshkent 2010y.

Kurpayanidi K.I.
Professor of Economics Department
Academician of International Academy
of Theoretical and Applied Sciences (USA),
Fergana Polytechnic Institute
Mikhaylov A.B.
3rd year student
Faculty of Management in Production,
Fergana Polytechnic Institute
E-mail: antinari@gmail.com

INDUSTRY 4.0 AND ITS IMPACT ON CROSS-BORDER INVESTMENT: NEW CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

Today's era of Industry 4.0 is a key driver of the changes taking place in the business environment. The term affects international value chains, foreign direct investment flows, business models and the functioning of both high-tech and traditional companies, including multinationals¹. The term Industry 4.0 was introduced in Germany in 2011 and marks the beginning of the fourth industrial revolution. The initiative is a global project, first introduced in German industry and then transformed internationally. Although several definitions of Industry 4.0 have been proposed, most researchers emphasise the use of digital technology to optimise and integrate production processes. As in previous industrial revolutions, this fourth revolution is the result of breakthrough innovations that improve manufacturing ecosystems by making them more intensive and connected².

New Industry 4.0 technologies are making a significant contribution to cross-border flows of foreign direct investment. These innovations help to reduce distances between nations, accelerate information exchange and open up new opportunities for direct investment. They accelerate decision-making, share experience and knowledge, improve the quality of products and services and increase production efficiency. As a result, foreign direct investment flows become more flexible and adaptive to changing market conditions.

On the one hand, Industry 4.0 increases the attractiveness of countries for investors interested in developing high-tech industries, which may lead to increased direct investment flows to these countries. On the other hand, these technologies also contribute to the development of local markets and strengthen local economies, which may lead to reduced investment flows to other countries. In addition, Industry 4.0

¹ Khan, S. A. R., Razaq, A., Yu, Z., & Miller, S. (2021). Industry 4.0 and circular economy practices: A new era business strategies for environmental sustainability. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 30(8), 4001-4014.

² De Beule, F., & Nauwelaerts, Y. (2013). Innovation and creativity: statement of the issues. In *Innovation and Creativity* (pp. 1-14). Edward Elgar Publishing.

offers new opportunities for cross-border investments, such as joint ventures and technology partnerships. This can help companies from different countries combine their strengths and resources to develop new technologies and products¹.

Industry 4.0 technologies are now having a significant impact on traditional industries and markets, leading to major changes in the global economy and business landscape. These changes are also impacting foreign direct investment flows, providing companies and investors with new opportunities and challenges in shaping business models. Industry 4.0 is also leading to a change in the scale and direction of foreign direct investment. For example, the use of online technology reduces the need for large investments in marketing and sales, as online content providers take over much of the work involved in collecting and providing data. As a result, production can become more centralised and localised rather than dispersed along global value chains.

With the rapid development of Industry 4.0 technologies, individual businesses are rethinking their criteria for making decisions about investing in other countries. Investors will choose foreign direct investment locations based on new factors that will become more important in light of these changes.

On the other hand, Industry 4.0 also opens up new opportunities for direct investment, such as joint ventures and technology partnerships that allow companies to combine their strengths and resources to develop new technologies and products.

Industry 4.0 may lead to a shift of focus away from cheap labour in developing countries and thus make this factor less relevant to investors seeking FDI. For example, if a Japanese company is looking for a location to locate its production that can be automated rather than labour-based, it is more likely to choose manufacturing on its premises.

The digital aspect will be a key factor for investors planning to use Industry 4.0 technologies in their businesses. As technology grows and companies restructure, highly skilled human capital will become more important and possibly become a driving force for FDI. Greater automation in manufacturing will displace low-skilled workers but increase demand for more skilled professionals such as programmers, engineers and big data analysts. Low-skilled workers may be replaced or laid off as a result of production automation. A highly skilled workforce will become more important because it will stimulate further innovation.

As technological innovation advances, costs can be further reduced and efficiency improved. As such, FDI flows may increase significantly in regions where technological capabilities are concentrated. Such changes will require companies and governments to adapt their investment policies to ensure a favourable climate for investors. Administrative procedures can also be simplified to improve the investment environment.

Thus, at present, one of the key effects that could arise from the diffusion of Industry 4.0 technologies is the shift of productive activities from developing and transition economies to developed countries. No longer will the availability of cheap labour be used as a determining factor in choosing where to invest. Recipient countries must therefore take additional measures to improve the investment climate.

Boboyev Akmal Choriyevich
Buxoro muhandislik-texnologiya
instituti dotsenti, iqtisod fanlari nomzodi,
E-mail: boboev-akmal@bk.ru
Akramova Obida Qosimovna
E-mail: akramova3932@gmail.com
Buxoro muhandislik-texnologiya
instituti doktoranti

O`ZBEKISTON YENGIL SANOATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA INVESTITSIYAVIY JOZIBADORLIKNING O`RNI VA AHAMIYATI

O`zbekistonda yengil sanoat tarmoqlarini rivojlantirish, ishlab chiqarilayotgan tayyor mahsulotlarning turlari va assortimentini kengaytirish, shuningdek, tarmoq korxonalarining investitsiya va

¹ Kurpayanidi, K. I. (2023). Интеграция инновационной деятельности и икт как источник трансформации. *Nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar xalqaro jurnali*, 3 (2), 45-55. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7699541>

Курманов Н.А., Рахимбекова А.Е., Сатбаева А.Ж., Алиев У.Ж., Жагалбаев Б.Т. Организация инновационной деятельности на предприятиях обрабатывающей промышленности Казахстана .123	123
Salayev San'atbek Kamilovich, Rajapov Xayrulla Bekdurdiyevich. Intensiv usulda baliq yetishtirish orqali iqtisodiy samaradorlikga erishish	125
Mirzaev Qulmamat Djanzakovich, Rabbimova Maftuna Mehriddin qizi. Innovatsion iqtisodiyot asosida rivojlantirishda mulkdorlar munosabatini o'rni	127
Ш.Х.Мухитдинов. Туризмга хизмат кўрсатиш соҳаси элементлари иерархик кўриниши ва уларни моделлари	129
Bekzhanova Toty Kalzhanovna, Altynbek Berik Atakonysuly. The current state of innovative entrepreneurship in Kazakhstan.....	130
Yeshpanova Dinara Daurenbekovna, Turginbayeva Alua Smagulovna. Theoretical aspects of the innovation process in Kazakhstan	132
Кузнецова Эльвира Рудольфовна, Олимова Нодира Хамракуловна. Актуальные научные проблемы экономики России	134
Мухаммедов Мурод Мухаммедович, Мухаммедова Зарина Муродовна. Хизмат кўрсатиш соҳасини жадал ривожлантиришнинг зарурати.....	137
У.Р.Матякубов. Оролбўйи минтақасида археологик туризмни ривожлантириш имкониятлари....	138
Сафаров Бахтиёр Джуракулович, Дадабаев Кучкар Абдуллаевич. Современные тенденции и критические риски в развитии предприятий розничной торговли в условиях цифровой экономики и пути их снижения	140
Toxirov Javlon Raximovich. Iqtisodiy fanlarni o'qitishda xorij tajribasidan foydalanish imkoniyatlari .142	142
Kurpayanidi K.I., Mikhaylov A.B. Industry 4.0 and its impact on cross-border investment: new challenges and opportunities	145
Boboyev Akmal Choriyevich, Akramova Obida Qosimovna. O'zbekiston yengil sanoatini rivojlantirishda investitsiyaviy jozibadorlikning o'rni va ahamiyati.....	146
Boboyev Akmal Choriyevich, Akramova Obida Qosimovna. Hududlarning investitsion jozibadorligini oshirish orqali mamlakatning iqtisodiy o'sishini ta'minlash masalalari	148
Achilov Abror Niyatqobilovich, Najmiddinova Muslima Azamat qizi. O'zbekistonda korxonalar, tashkilotlarni xususiyashtirish va ishlab chiqarishni rivojlantirish masalalari.	150
Қиличов Бобир Хўжакул ўғли. Хизмат кўрсатиш соҳаси бўлган суғурта ташкилотларида бошқарув самарадорлигининг омилли таҳлили	151
Kuvandikov Aziz Ravshanovich. Economic impacts of developing halal +m.i.c.e tourism in bukhara destination.	154
A.Ch.Abdiev, A.A.Alimardonov, A.A.Alimardonov. Raqamli iqtisodiyot va inson omili.....	156
Саипназаров Шербек Шайлаббекович. Молия инжиниринг орқали янги банк маҳсулотларини тадбиқ этиш масалалари	158
Хидирова Гавҳар Рустамовна. Минтақани етакчи тармоғи туризмни ривожлантиришнинг тизимли муаммолари	159
З.Б. Навруз-зода, “Смарт туристик дестинация” зиёрат кластерини шакллантириш.	161
Рашидов Мэлс Каримович. Эркин иқтисодий ва кичик саноат зоналари фаолиятини такомиллаштиришнинг долзарблиги	163
Gulrukh Djumanazarovna Khasanova, Sohibjon Sobirovich Sadirov. Mehnat resurslari: shakllanishi va ulardan samarali foydalanish yo'llari	166
Zaripov Bahodir Bobomurod o'g'li. Ma'lumotlarni saqlashda bulutli texnologiyalarni qo'llash	167
Jahongir Qosimov. O'zbekistonda raqamli iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish davr talabi	169
Abdullayev Islom Botirovich. Milliy iqtisodiyotni barqaror o'sishini ta'minlashda klaster tizimini raqobatbardoshligini oshirish	172
Djurayeva Nafisa Bakhodirovna. Halal certification practices in food and services.....	175
Арипова Махлиё Салахиддиновна. Бренд как инструмент эффективного продвижения продукта на рынок товаров и услуг	177
Toirova Nozima. Turistik destsinatsiyalarni boshqarish asosida turistik mintaqalarni rivojlantirish	179
J.T.Umirov. O'zbekistonda agroturizmni rivojlantirish masalalari.....	180
А.А.Қодиров. Инновацион усуллардан фойдаланиш орқали экологик туризмни самарали ривожлантириш йўллари	182
Уракова Махсад Хакимовна. Совершенствование управленческого учета на предприятиях АПК .185	185
Oripova Gulirano Nodirovna. The influence of stochastic processes and synergetic effects on the formation of competitive advantages in domestic trade.....	186